

Speculation on Why Special Relativity/Interaction Yields E, p, but also \hbar/E and \hbar/p

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Newtonian mechanics establishes the notions of kinetic energy ($pp/2m_0$) and momentum $p=mv$. These two interaction quantities arise by a force acting on a mass m_0 . For example, they could act on a rest mass. The force does not act on x and t which are reference variables so to speak. Such is not the case in special relativity. If one has a particle with m_0 at $x=0, t$, then seen from a moving frame, it has E, p , but it is understood that a physical interaction (force) had to be applied to actually get it to move. The frame approach produces the values-/
 $E=m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, but it does not remove the physical nature of an interaction. The frame approach, however, also changes $x=0, t$ to x', t' and so we argue that these changes must also be consequences of a physical interaction. One cannot state that the interaction changes m_0 to E, p (consistent with a frame moving with $-v$) and then argue that the frame changes x, t to x', t' with no association with an interaction. We argue here that there must be an interaction related consequence to $x, t \rightarrow x', t'$. The question is: What is it?

We argue that the change from x, t to new values x', t' during an interaction leads to the notion of an uncertainty in x and t values. E and p are new values which are linked to specific interactions. E is linked with the amount of energy a particle has (i.e it could be linked to temperature increases in a gas) etc, while p is associated with target impulse hits. These are physically different and two particles with E_1, p and E_2, p yield the same impulse target hit, but change temperature in different manners. x and t are not interaction variables and their change (associated with some uncertainty in their values during the interaction it seems as they change to x', t') seems unconnected to an interaction. It is only through the combination of E, p and x', t' in the Lorentz invariant $-Et' + px'$ that one may see that shifts in t' and x' can leave the invariant unchanged. It is not that E and p change values, but the interaction which changes x, t to x', t' may introduce uncertainty into x', t' , i.e x', t' and $x' + \hbar/p, t' + \hbar/E$ yield the same Lorentz invariant value. This means that E and p may act at stochastic t and x values, we suggest. One expects that some kind of interaction effect must be associated with the force interaction because it changes m_0 to E, p , but also changes x, t to x', t' and this must have interaction consequences as well.

We further argue that there exist different interaction/measuring approaches which detect these different interaction consequences. For a photon, E is associated with absorption, while p is linked with an impulse hit on a target. \hbar/p , however, yields an interference pattern which is also associated with an interaction albeit in a probabilistic manner. This occurs because the effect of the interaction on changing x, t to x', t' is linked with uncertainty in the actual x and t values during the interaction. In Newtonian mechanics there is complete certainty as there is only one set of x, t values.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics describes the effects of forces and uses the interaction variables:

$$p = mv = \text{momentum} = \int F dt \quad \text{and} \quad pp/2m_0 = \text{kinetic energy} = \int F dx \quad ((1))$$

A stationary m_0 will give rise to p and ke during and after an interaction. X and t are measuring variables, not interaction variables, and do not change in Newtonian mechanics.

The interaction can only convert m_0 into p and E . These two variables are physically measured in different ways. P is associated with an impulse hit on a target while E could be linked with an increase in temperature (average kinetic energy) in a gas. Two particles with the same p and different E values yield the same impulse hit, but different temperature increases. As far as Newtonian mechanics goes, E and p are the interaction variables.

Special Relativity

Special relativity is often associated with viewing particles from different moving frames. In particular, one could view a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t from a frame moving at $-v$. There is no explicit force present, but the person in the moving frame would see m_0 move at v and have an energy. In fact, using the Lorentz transformation one may show that

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((2))$$

These become $E = m_0 c^2 + ke$ and $p = m_0 v$ in the $v \ll c$ limit. This is a direct link to Newton's results and the idea of a force interaction. We argue that one cannot separate the values E and p from the notion of an interaction.

The issue that arises with special relativity is that the Lorentz transformation may be derived simply thinking in terms of the transformation of $x=0, t$ to x', t' such that

$$x' = vt' \quad ((3))$$

The Lorentz 2×2 matrix may be obtained solely for x, t with no notion of an interaction. This, however, is also an incomplete view because the same matrix transforms m_0 to E, p and so we argue that one must think of an interaction (i.e. force) as changing $x=0, t$ to x', t' . The key idea of this note is that if an interaction changes x, t as well as m_0 and if m_0 manifests itself in two new interaction variables E, p , then the change in x, t must also be linked with an interaction related consequence. X', t' , however, are clearly not interaction variables. Their change, it seems, may only be linked with shifts or uncertainty in x and t . E, p are fixed values, but given $x=0, t$ and x', t' such that $x' = vt$, one might ask: What are the x and t values during the interaction? It seems that there is uncertainty. One may quantify this uncertainty if one considers E, p, x', t' together, i.e. in a Lorentz invariant

$$-Et' + px' \quad ((4))$$

We have argued before that ((4)) has the same value for

$$X', t' \quad \text{and} \quad x' + \hbar/p, \quad t' + \hbar/E \quad ((5))$$

In principle, one might argue that this is simply a math statement with no physical relevance. We suggest that there must be interactional relevance as the change from x,t to x',t' following the frame comparison is equivalent to a physical force acting on the particle. It is the physical force then that must change x,t to x',t' just as it changes m_0 to E,p and there must be an interactional consequence.

Given that x,t changes to x',t' , leading to uncertainty in time and space, this suggests a probabilistic scenario. E and p are still the interaction variables and x' and t' are not, so how can x',t' uncertainty affect E,p . Furthermore $x'=vt'$ does not seem to indicate any uncertainty. The uncertainty is present in the change from $x=0,t$ to x',t' and in ((5)) and so we propose an Lorentz invariant probability

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((6))$$

This suggests that E interactions may be linked with probabilistic time points and p interactions with probabilistic x impulse hit points. We have argued that ((6)) is linked with conservation of E and p because it considers t and x as independent probabilistic variables and

$$\exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = \exp(ip_3x)\exp(ip_4x) \text{ and a similar expression for } \exp(-iEt) \quad ((7))$$

We note that the notion of conservation of energy and momentum is already present in the four-vector because (in one dimension)

$$(p_1, E_1) + (p_2, E_2) = (p_3, E_3) + (p_4, E_4) \text{ if } p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4 \text{ and } E_1+E_2 = E_3+E_4 \quad ((8))$$

Thus, ((6)) is not introduced to enforce conservation of energy and momentum. Rather it is a consequence of the uncertainty in x and t introduced by the force interaction which converts x,t to x',t' and m_0 to E,p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is well-known in Newtonian mechanics, that a force acting on a rest mass m_0 may create a momentum $p=mv$ and a kinetic energy $ke=pp/2m_0$. These are interaction variables and manifest themselves physically in different manners. P is linked with impulse hits on a target, while kinetic energy could be linked with temperature etc.

Special relativity is an approach which considers a rest mass m_0 from a frame moving with constant speed $-v$. This leads to expressions $E=m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. In the $v \ll c$ limit, one finds $E = m_0cc + ke$ and $p=mv$. Physically the frame approach must be equivalent to a force interaction. In Newtonian mechanics there is only one set x,t . In special relativity $x=0, t$ transforms to x',t' such that $x'=vt'$. We argue that this must be seen as a consequence of the interaction and must have interaction related consequences itself similar to E and p . X' and t' , however, are not interaction variables and it seems that uncertainty in their values (going from $x=0, t$ to x',t') in the interaction is the only effect. If one considers the Lorentz invariant $-Et'+px'$ (which combines E,p,x',t'), then one may see this uncertainty in x',t' idea at work because x',t' and $x'+\hbar/p$ and $t'+\hbar/E$ both yield the same value. In other words, the

interaction introduces a time-space uncertainty for E and p interactions. E is linked with probabilistic time and p with probabilistic x. Thus, p is a measure of the impulse hit, but a stochastic x means that this hit may be delivered probabilistically at different x points. We have discussed the notion of quantum mechanics being linked to special relativity in previous notes, but here we argue specifically that the effect of a force (equivalent to viewing from a frame moving at -v) must also apply to $x=0$, t changing to x',t' and that one is forced to seek an interactional effect of this change. In other words, special relativity shows that it is not complete to simply consider no change to E,p, but that there has to be an interactional effect of the uncertainty change of $x=0$, t to x',t' during the interaction. We argue that it is the feature which leads to the quantum mechanical probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$